

A review of the Marine Biological Collections in Spain.

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G2: General, Lecture Theatre 1, Appleton Tower, 11 Crichton Street, EH8 9LE, June 7, 2022, 11:30 AM - 1:00 PM

Marine biological collections are key to scientific research and to assess the still poorly known biodiversity of our seas and oceans. The value of their specimens is, in many cases, incalculable or priceless e.g. deep-sea specimens, whose fieldwork costs are immense and/or specimens from areas that will probably never be sampled again. Samplings in the ocean are mostly unrepeatable or irreproducible, beside the fact that the marine environment is difficult and very expensive to access, especially in deeper waters, which make marine collections exceptional. Having marine specimens available for research and biodiversity studies in a collection's room is therefore a luxury.

Despite their importance and value, marine collections are usually underfunded, for periods of time with no employees, there is a lack of specific qualification for curators and managers and fewer and fewer specialists in taxonomy, illustrators or photographers. Marine collections are not sufficiently recognized in the field of collections and receive little attention in the discussions associated with global biodiversity. The proper conservation of the marine scientific samples and the access to the specimens and their associated data is key to our collective understanding of biological diversity, especially now in the Decade of the Oceans. A correct management is urgent in light of increasing environmental change and the need for more effective conservation measures.

In Spain we recognize four collections dedicated entirely to marine fauna: Biological Reference Collections of the Marine Sciences Institute of Barcelona, Marine Fauna Collection of Oceanographic Center of Canarias, Marine Fauna of Oceanographic Center of Málaga, Crustacean Collection of Oceanographic Center of Cadiz. In which catalogued specimens are well preserved, identified by expert taxonomists, available for research and loans, and their data publicly available at international biodiversity portals (e.g. GBIF). To address the aforementioned deficiencies, we propose a network of Marine Biological Collections in Spain to build cooperation, strength collaborations and promoting scientific best practices for the management of these collections. It's necessary to join forces for raising awareness of marine collections and their benefits to science, promoting sustainable funding mechanisms to support collections and international collaborations among marine collections, their staff and researchers.

